

ANALYSIS OF ARABIC SPIRITUAL EXPRESSIONS USED IN THE WISDOM OF AHMED YASSAVI

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Annotation: the purpose of this work is to help students who do not know the Arabic literary language to understand the Arabic words and phrases used in many places in the wisdom of A. Yassavi, referring to the Holy Qur'an and Hadith. At the same time, it is one of the tasks of the scientific article to reveal the analysis of mystical expressions to a certain extent to the readers.

Key words:the wisdom of A.Yassavi, spirituality, peace, poetic divan, mystical and philosophical gems

INTRODUCTION

It is known that it is difficult to imagine life without spirituality. In this sense, the wisdom of Ahmed Yassavi serves as a starting point for divine guidance for many Turkic peoples, after the Qur'an and the hadiths of the Lord of the Universe, Fakhru'l Mursaliyn, Sayyidul Anbiyyah Muhammad Mustafa, may God bless him and grant him peace. The great thinker Hazrat Alisher Navoi and many other scholars have noted this with respect and reverence in their works.

Even in today's fast-paced world, the priceless legacy of our great grandfather has a special place in our spiritual life. These wisdoms, which call a person to spiritual purity, pure faith and belief, are a valuable resource, especially in the responsible and extremely important task of educating the young generation. We see the relevance of this work even more clearly in the example of wars and unrest in a number of countries.

Our great grandfather has been revered in our country since ancient times. Despite

the prohibitions of the former regime, academician I. Mominov, one of our scientists, covered this topic to a certain extent in the 50s of the last century. Later, in the early 70s, philological sciences

BACKGROUND KNOWLEDGE

Qutbul-Aqtab of the saints of Turonzamin, the founder of the Yassawiya order, Shaykhul Mashoyikh, the perfect elder, Sheikh Khoja Ahmad Yassawi left a great spiritual legacy. The work "Devoni Hikmat" of this breed of Babarakot has been revered and read with love in the whole Turkic world for almost a thousand years. This poetic divan, which consists of mystical and philosophical gems, is very famous among the Turkic people because it is written in a very fluent and simple language. Dr. Ergash Rustamov's article "The sound of history and life in the wisdom of Ahmad Yassavi" was published.

In 1987-1991, excerpts and articles from wisdom published in a number of publications introduced the Uzbek reader more closely to this work. In 1991-1995, it was published in the Turkish cities of Ankara and Istanbul, which pleased many.

The publication of Hikmat several times in our country has been an excellent light upon light. Let's be thankful that today I. Khaqqul, Q. Sodikov, T. Qoraev and M. Eshmuhamedova, among our great scientists, have carried out serious research in the scientific study and analysis of A. Yassavi's "Divoni Hikmat" and created the direction of Yassavi studies.

METHODOLOGY

It can be believed that knowing the translation of Arabic words and phrases is a necessary tool for understanding the wisdom of Purmana and getting spiritual nourishment.

Arabic words and expressions are widely used in "Devoni Hikmat" by Ahmed Yassavi. It is clearly visible that the main content of wisdom is a set of philosophical knowledge leading to guidance. In this sense, the basis of wisdom is

God's only divinity, his word, the verses of the Holy Qur'an, and the divine secrets revealed in the hadith of our Prophet Muhammad Mustafa (S.A.V).

Since the Qur'an and hadiths are in Arabic, the Arabic words and phrases in the wisdoms contain deep philosophical meanings, which increased the scientific value of the work even more.

Shaykh Ahmed Yassavi, who attained the status of perfection in the science of Sufism, was undoubtedly a connoisseur of Arabic, Persian, and Turkish languages.

DATA COLLECTION AND ANALYSIS

The most important thing is that the deep religious-philosophical meanings of these Arabic words and phrases are given in a simple and fluent Turkish with sincerity and love to the extent of captivating the reader.

Shaykh Ahmed Yassavi, who reached the status of Piri Kamil in the Tariqat, is considered to be the Kutbul Aktob of the Guardians of Turonzamin. Undoubtedly, the merits of Sheikh Khwaja Yusuf Hamadani (r.a.), the teachers of this great nobleman, are incomparable in this Qurbati ilakhi. It is not for nothing that this breed of bobarakot is recognized as the teacher of Central Asian scholars.

The famous Uzbek enlightener and poet Abdurauf Fitrat also expressed good opinions about our grandfather A. Yassavi in the article.

"In the fifth century of the Hijri, a man named Yusuf Hamadani, who was born in a place near the city of Hamadan in Iran, studied religious sciences, became a famous scholar, and was devoted to Sufism. Such a mullah - a mystic, built houses in the cities of Marv, Bukhara, and Samarkand (Samarkand) and began to serve as a sheikh. Our Ahmad Yassavi is also the third half-brother of Yusuf Hamadani.

According to one tradition, Ahmed Yassavi was born in the city of Yassi (today's Turkestan), according to another tradition, in Sayram. It is not known when he was born, but he died in 562 A.H.

After four hundred years, come out and be an ummah,
How many years will you serve the European people,
referring to the verse, it is possible to judge that he was born in the second half of the fourth century Hijri.

Yassavi's father was an Eshan named Sheikh Ibrahim, who died when he was young. The orphaned Yassavi is older than Arslanbab, one of the famous sheikhs of that time. After the death of Arslanbob, our Yassavi came to Bukhara in search of pir, and met Yusuf Hamadoni, who is mentioned above, and became his disciple. After the death of Yusuf Hamadani, he became the third caliph in Bukhara. After a while, he handed over the Bukhara sheikhdom to Yusuf Hamdan's fourth caliph, Abdulkhalih Gijduvani, and returned to Yassi himself. Then he collected many murids from the people of the field, opened a khanaqah, and became a sheikh. Yasavi's writing of proverbs, not in the weight and style of Persian literature, but in the Turkish national weight, in the style of folk literature, must have started after returning to this shul Yassi, after the gathering of murids from the field people. When Yassavi reached the age of sixty-three, he dug an underground cellar in his house, went into it, and pretended to be cut off from the world, and he continued the sheikhdom and died there. He died in the year 562 Hijri.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

They were analyzed in a beautiful Turkish way so that the reader can deeply understand and think about the contents of the Qur'an and the hadiths of Sayyidul Mursaliyn (S.A.V.) in Arabic words and phrases.

Considering that the philosophy of life is very broad and complex, we believe that it is very important for the reader to understand the meanings of these words. These Arabic words and phrases used by Ahmed Yassavi among the Turkish text are mostly references to the Qur'an and hadiths, the history of mankind, and the original world theology. It is known that Quranic and Nabi words take place in the

reader's heart and start him to get closer to the Creator and divine guidance. According to His Holiness Yassavi, these wisdoms will heal the mental and physical ailments of the student. For a thousand years, the Turkic peoples have been reciting these wisdoms with love and reverence.

Even today, in a time when it is clear that there is no bright future without faith, without a spiritually mature ideology, without a pure Islamic creed, the wisdom of Ahmed Yassavi is of great educational significance.

Scholars have recognized that the highest status of karomat is good manners in accordance with the Sunnah of our Lord Muhammad (S.A.W.). It is at this point that the author noted the importance of these wisdoms in the perfect performance of this responsible task, that is, the manners of servitude. It is clear that the author, who fulfilled the beautiful Sunnah of saving the people of faith from hell with great dedication and knowledge, was a scholar of the human psyche.

In Nozimjon Iminjonov's collection of wisdom "Wisdom is what the believer has lost", the following definition is given:

Hikmat is an Arabic word that means to say one word in the right place, to the right person, in the right amount, or to do something on time, with sufficient care.

Wisdom is one of the ways to know God.

Wisdom is the quality of all the Prophet and scholars who follow his knowledge.

A person who speaks with wisdom and performs his actions with wisdom is called a wise man. Commonly used Arabic terms: Bismillah, hikmat, talib, riyazat.

Qutbul-aqtabi of Turonzamin saints, sarwari mashoyih, founder of Yassaviya order, perfect elder Sheikh Khoja Ahmed Yassavi is a great thinker and scientist who made a great contribution to the development of the culture, history and spirituality of the Turkic peoples. All Turkic peoples have the right to be proud of this breed.

CONCLUSION

A. Yassavi's work "Devoni hikmat" is a scientific and mystical source that people

have been reading since the 10th century. It embodies the idea of a perfect human being, the ideology of Islam, the verses of the Qur'an, the Sunnah of our master Muhammad (S.A.W.), and many instructive, wise, and philosophical meanings. Naturally, the Qur'an and the hadiths of our Prophet Muhammad (S.A.W.), which were revealed in Arabic, should be explained to the Turkish language reader. Our intention is to explain to the reader the Arabic expressions skillfully used in this work.

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